

Detection of *Streptococcus agalactiae* in Milk from Apparently Healthy Animals within Sokoto Metropolis

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This study was conducted to isolate and identify *Streptococcus agalactiae* in milk from clinically non-mastitis animal within Sokoto metropolis. 200 milk samples were collected from dairy farms and households within the metropolis. *Streptococcus agalactiae* were identified in the milk samples collected by culture and isolation methods. Gram staining and microscopy were also used to determine the gram reaction and morphological characteristics of *Streptococcus agalactiae* respectively. Beta-haemolysis and catalase tests were conducted on positive isolates to further biochemically confirm the isolates. Results indicated a 12.5% detection rate which is suggestive of subclinical mastitis caused by the agents. Therefore, herd level control and eradication of sub-clinical mastitis especially targeted against *Streptococcus agalactiae* should be implemented by the farms, households and the government at large.

Keywords: Public health, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, Mastitis, Sokoto metropolis, morphological characteristic.

INTRODUCTION

Dairy products, especially milk, are one of the important food sources in many countries of the world (Cobirka *et al.*, 2020). The need to increase the average milk yield per dairy animal is driven by the growing global demand for dairy products, and this has resulted in genetic selection and improvement in dairy nutrition and management. One of the greatest problems associated with decreased milk yield is poor udder health, most especially due to mastitis (Cobirka *et al.*, 2020).

Mastitis refers to the parenchyma inflammation of the mammary gland, characterized by physical, chemical and bacteriological changes in the milk and pathological changes in the glandular tissue of the mammary gland (Junaidu *et al.*, 2011). Nigeria cattle population was estimated to be 13 million and livestock in general account for 5% of Gross Domestic Product (Junaidu *et*

al., 2011). Milk produced from such categories of animals represent a significant dietary source for rural communities as well as a considerable amount for urban and pre-urban population (Junaidu *et al.*, 2011). Mastitis can be categorised into two, subclinical or clinical mastitis, which is classified based on the disease severity or contagiousness and environmental prevalence of the causative agents (Furgasa *et al.*, 2019). Clinical mastitis is characterised by gross changes in milk, physical abnormalities of the udder and systemic involvement in cow. Sub clinical mastitis is associated with absence of gross lesions and a surge in somatic cells amount in the milk. It is more prevalent compare to clinical mastitis and the infection over a longer period of time present reduced production and decreased quality of milk produced (Mulugeta andWassie, 2013).

According to Mulugeta and Wassie (2013), the diagnosis of bovine mastitis could be performed by clinical examination (inspection and palpation) of the udder for clinical forms of mastitis, screening (California Mastitis Test test

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for subclinical forms of mastitis and bacterial isolation is used for confirmatory diagnosis. The risk factors of mastitis are based upon four components; exposure to microbes, cow defence mechanisms, environmental and management factors (Furgasa *et al.*, 2019). Bovine mastitis is one of the major economic disease of dairy cattle throughout the globe, caused majorly by *Streptococcus agalactiae* which is also termed as Group B *Streptococcus* (GBS) (Yang *et al.*, 2013). *Streptococcus agalactiae* is a Gram-positive pathogen usually associated with neonatal meningitis in humans, meningo-encephalitis in fish and large animals, and bovine mastitis which is the most prevalent health disorder causing severe milk loss, and notable financial losses in the dairy industry (Pang *et al.*, 2017).

Unlike *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus agalactiae* is a mastitis bacterium that can grow and multiply in the mammary gland, however, it can survive for a short period of time on hands, milking machine components, and teat skin, causing its transmission from cow to cow during milking (Lakew *et al.*, 2019). This bacterium primarily infects the cisterns and the ductal system of the mammary gland. An irritant is produced, responsible for the inflammation of the gland which is mostly subclinical with occasional clinical symptoms (Amosun *et al.*, 2010). The infection is mostly introduced into a clean herd when an infected cow is purchased and due to the silent nature of the infection and highly contagious nature, infections could be spread rapidly (Furgasa *et al.*, 2019). Other incriminated causative agents from mastitis milk samples include *Staphylococcus aureus*, other *Streptococcus* (*Streptococcus uberis* and *Streptococcus dysgalactiae*), and members of the family Enterobacteriaceae are among the most common etiological agents in cows and other animal species (Lakew *et al.*, 2019). Mastitis is a major problem in the area of study (Sokoto State) which is the second largest producer of livestock in Nigeria and also represent a significant percentage in the consumption of milk and milk products (Junaidu *et al.*, 2011). The study will therefore provide information on the extent to which *Streptococcus agalactiae* causes mastitis in Sokoto state. Furthermore, veterinarians within the state can utilise the result of this research to draw an effective herd health management protocol. The study aimed to isolate and identify *Streptococcus agalactiae* from milk samples, by confirming the cellular morphology of *Streptococcus agalactiae* using Gram staining and biochemically characterise the isolates using catalase test.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area includes farms and selected houses within Sokoto state metropolis. The metropolis is made

up of Sokoto North and South local government areas. Also, some parts of Dange Shuni, Wamakko local government, and Kware local government constitute parts of the metropolis.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted to isolate and identify *Streptococcus agalactiae* from fresh milk samples of clinically non mastitis animal within the metropolis. Sampling of individual animal was based on random sampling method. The risk factors considered at the study were age, parity, lactation stage, breed and hygienic milking.

Clinical Inspection and Preparation of Udder for Sample Collection

Udders or teats were physically examined first by visualization and then by palpation to check for lesions, fibrosis, swelling, inflammation, visible injury, tick infestation, tissue atrophy and any blindness. The appearance and viscosity of milk secretion from each quarter were examined for watery secretions. The hands were cleaned with detergents and clean water, the udder and teats were also cleaned by clean water and dried by using clean towel before the sample collection. Recontamination of the teat during scrub was avoided. The teat on the far side of the udder was cleaned first before those on the near side. Scrubbing was stopped only after the towel appears clean.

Materials and Equipment

Sterile test tubes, conical flasks, cultured plates, glass slides, slant bottles, milk samples, peptone water, nutrient agar, sheep blood, hydrogen peroxide, distilled water, crystal violet, Lugol's iodine, alcohol, safranin, oil immersion, incubator, hot air oven, hot plate, autoclave, refrigerator and microscope.

Sample Collection

A total of 200 milk samples were randomly collected from Red Sokoto Goat, white Fulani, Sokoto Gudali, and Friesian respectively (Table 1). To reduce contamination of the teat ends during sample collection, the near teats were sampled first before the far ones. The milk samples were then collected into sterile containers after discarding the first 3 milking streams. Then, the samples were placed and preserved in an ice box and transported to the Veterinary Public Health Laboratory, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto for storage in a refrigerator.

Isolation and Identification of *Streptococcus agalactiae*

The milk samples were pre-enriched using peptone water

Table 1: Showing the number of samples collected across different species and breeds.

Study Breeds	Number of Animals	Number of Samples
Red Sokoto Goat	6	12
White Fulani cow	15	60
Sokoto Gudali cow	24	96
Friesian cow	8	32
Total	6 Goats, 47 Cows	200

Plate 1: Cultured nutrient agar plate.

(in a ratio of 1ml milk sample into 9ml of peptone water) in sterile test tubes and then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. A loopful of the pre-enriched milk samples were streaked onto prepared nutrient agar plates and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. After 24 hours, the growths on nutrient agar plates were sub-cultured on blood agar (using 95% nutrient agar with 5% sterile sheep blood). Blood agar plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The plates were examined afterward for gross colonial morphology, haemolytic characteristics (narrow zones of beta-haemolysis) after 24 hours were observed as positive result.

Positive isolates were then characterised via Gram staining as gram positive cocci in chain form. Presumptive colonies of *Streptococcus agalactiae* were selected and slanted on nutrient agar in sterile slant bottles, incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, removed and stored inside refrigerator.

Biochemical Examination Using Catalase Test

Using a sterile inoculating wire loop, growths from positive slanted isolates were inoculated in a grease-free

glass slide. One drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide was added and homogenized gently. Observation for bubble formation was done. Rapid and sustained appearance of bubbles or effervescence indicate a positive test (Reiner, 2010) while catalase negative test (no bubble formation) is considered positive test for *Streptococcus agalactiae*.

RESULTS

Culture on Nutrient Agar

A total of 200 milk samples were collected within Sokoto Metropolis and processed in the veterinary public health laboratory and 178 samples (89%) from the total milk collected yielded positive growths on nutrient agar following incubation at 37°C for 24 hours as seen in Plate 1.

Sub-Culture on Blood Agar

One hundred and seventy-eight samples (89%) that yielded growth on nutrient agar were sub-cultured on

Plate 2: Cultured blood agar plate in an incubator.

Plate 3: Narrow zone of beta hemolysis (black arrow)

blood agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. 36 culture plates (18%) were seen with narrow zones of beta hemolysis, indicative for *Streptococcus agalactiae* while the remaining 142 culture plates were seen with alpha

zones of hemolysis (with greenish zones). The 36 beta-hemolytic isolates were preserved in slant bottles for subsequent analysis (Plate 2 and 3).

Following sub-culture, Gram-stained isolates appear as

Plate 4: Gram positive cocci in chain form (red arrow)

Table 2: The prevalence of *Streptococcus agalactiae* in relation to studied breeds.

Study Breeds	Number of samples collected	Positive Sample Number	Prevalence (%)
Red Sokoto Goat	12	4	16
White Fulani	60	7	28
Sokoto Gudali	96	10	40
Friesian	32	4	16
Total	200	25	12.5

purplish in colour under the microscope and are suggestive of Gram-positive cocci in chains. (Plate 4).

Biochemical Test (Catalase Test)

The 36 culture positive isolates were further subjected to catalase test where 25 (69.4%) shows positive results.

Prevalence of *Streptococcus agalactiae*

With regards to the total number of samples (200) collected, 25 samples yielded positive result for the above agent with a total prevalence of 12.5%. 4 samples

yielded positive for Red Sokoto Goat, White Fulani (7 samples), Sokoto Gudali (10 samples), and Friesian (4 samples), as presented in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

The present investigation demonstrated that 89% (178/200) of milk samples yielded bacterial growth on nutrient agar, indicating widespread microbial contamination of raw milk from apparently healthy animals. This high recovery rate reflects the intrinsic susceptibility of raw milk to microbial colonization due to

its rich nutrient composition, including lactose, proteins, and lipids that support rapid bacterial proliferation. From an epidemiological standpoint, such a high level of contamination is strongly indicative of lapses in hygienic milking practices, environmental sanitation, and post-harvest handling. Comparable findings have been reported in developing dairy systems where traditional husbandry practices predominate, with studies such as Gupta *et al.* (2024) linking high bacterial loads in milk to poor udder hygiene and contaminated milking utensils. Furthermore, the observation underscores the assertion by Martin *et al.* (2023) that subclinical infections often coexist with environmental contamination, thereby complicating the microbiological quality of raw milk. Importantly, the detection of bacterial growth in milk from clinically normal animals highlights the silent but epidemiologically significant role of subclinical mastitis reservoirs in dairy herds.

Upon sub-culture on blood agar, 18% (36/200) of isolates exhibited beta haemolysis, a key phenotypic marker associated with *Streptococcus agalactiae*. Beta haemolysis reflects the production of cytolytic toxins, particularly hemolysins, which facilitate tissue invasion and immune evasion. The proportion observed in this study aligns with reports by Monistero (2022), who documented similar haemolytic profiles among streptococcal isolates in bovine mastitis cases. However, the predominance of alpha haemolytic isolates (82%) suggests that *S. agalactiae* is not the sole etiological agent, reinforcing the polymicrobial etiology of mastitis. This is consistent with the findings of Bechtold (2025), who emphasized the coexistence of multiple mastitogenic bacteria including *Streptococcus uberis*, *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* and coliforms in dairy environments. The relatively lower proportion of beta haemolytic isolates in the present study may therefore reflect ecological competition among microbial populations, as well as variation in environmental and management conditions influencing pathogen dominance.

Microscopic characterization revealed Gram-positive cocci arranged in chains, which is consistent with the classical morphology of streptococci and supports the preliminary identification of *S. agalactiae*. This observation corroborates established microbiological criteria and aligns with previous reports such as Nikolova *et al.* (2022), who documented similar morphological features in mastitis-associated streptococci. From a pathogenicity perspective, the chain-forming arrangement enhances bacterial adherence and colonization within the mammary epithelium, thereby facilitating persistence and chronic infection. Additionally, the Gram-positive cell wall architecture, characterized by a thick peptidoglycan layer, contributes to resistance against environmental stressors and host immune responses. These structural attributes collectively explain the organism's ability to establish subclinical infections that remain undetected over

prolonged periods.

Biochemical confirmation using the catalase test showed that 69.4% (25/36) of presumptive isolates were catalase-negative, thereby confirming their identity as *Streptococcus agalactiae*. This step was critical in differentiating streptococci from catalase-positive organisms such as staphylococci, which may exhibit similar haemolytic patterns. The discrepancy between beta haemolytic isolates and catalase-negative confirmation highlights the limitations of relying solely on phenotypic characteristics for identification. Similar observations have been reported by Monistero (2022), who emphasized the necessity of integrating biochemical and, where possible, molecular techniques to improve diagnostic accuracy. The presence of catalase-positive isolates among presumptive colonies suggests either mixed infections or contamination, further reinforcing the complexity of mastitis microbiology.

The overall prevalence of *Streptococcus agalactiae* was 12.5%, indicating a moderate burden of subclinical mastitis within the study population. The prevalence was slightly lower to that of Junaidu *et al.* (2011) who reported 14.1% from selected commercial dairy farms within Sokoto metropolis, and higher than that of Gitau *et al.* (2014) who reported 7.7% in mastitis cow in Kenya. This prevalence less consistent with earlier reports from the same geographical region, including the 17.1% of Streptococcal spp. as reported by Nyakiti (2017), suggesting endemic persistence of the pathogen in Uasin Gishu County–Kenya dairy systems. From an epidemiological perspective, the persistence of *S. agalactiae* at this level is significant, given its highly contagious nature and ability to spread rapidly during milking through contaminated hands and equipment (Bechtold, 2025). Moreover, its role as a primary contagious pathogen distinguishes it from environmental mastitis agents, emphasizing the importance of herd-level control strategies.

Breed-specific analysis revealed a higher proportion of infection in Sokoto Gudali cattle (40%), followed by White Fulani (28%), with lower prevalence in Red Sokoto goats and Friesian breeds (16% each). This distribution suggests that host-related factors, including genetic susceptibility, udder conformation, and immune competence, may influence infection dynamics. Similar breed-associated variations have been documented by Lemal *et al.* (2025), who reported differential mastitis prevalence across cattle breeds due to both genetic and environmental interactions. The higher prevalence in Sokoto Gudali may also reflect management-related factors, such as exposure to communal grazing systems and suboptimal milking hygiene. Conversely, the relatively lower prevalence in Friesian breeds may be linked to improved management practices often associated with exotic or semi-intensive systems. These findings highlight the multifactorial nature of mastitis

epidemiology and underscore the need for targeted, breed-specific intervention strategies.

CONCLUSION

This study provides clear evidence that *Streptococcus agalactiae* is actively circulating in dairy herds within Sokoto metropolis, with a prevalence of 12.5% among apparently healthy animals. The detection of this pathogen in subclinical cases highlights its insidious nature and its capacity to persist undetected while contributing to reduced milk quality and productivity. The findings also confirm that raw milk serves as a potential vehicle for zoonotic transmission, posing significant public health risks, particularly in populations with high consumption of unpasteurized dairy products. The study further demonstrates that while conventional microbiological techniques remain valuable for pathogen identification, their limitations necessitate the adoption of more sensitive and specific diagnostic approaches, including molecular methods. Additionally, the observed variation in prevalence across breeds emphasizes the role of host and management factors in disease dynamics. In light of these findings, there is a critical need for comprehensive mastitis control programs that incorporate routine screening for subclinical infections, strict milking hygiene, and farmer education. Targeted interventions aimed at interrupting transmission pathways of *S. agalactiae* (particularly during milking) are essential for effective disease control. Ultimately, improving udder health management will not only enhance dairy productivity but also ensure the safety and quality of milk for public consumption.

REFERENCES

- Amosun, E. A., Ajuwape, A. T. P., and Adetosoye, A. I. (2010). Bovine streptococcal mastitis in Southwest and Northern states of Nigeria. *Afri. J. Biomed. Res.* 13(1):33–37.
- Bechtold, V. (2025). *Retrospective analysis of quarter milk samples from Bavaria: changes in the distribution of mastitis pathogens and antimicrobial resistance of Streptococcus dysgalactiae, Streptococcus agalactiae, and Streptococcus canis isolates between 2012 and 2023* (Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, LMU, Munchen).
- Cheng, W. N., and Han, S. G. (2020). Bovine mastitis: risk factors, therapeutic strategies, and alternative treatments — A review. *Asian-Australasian J. Animal Sci.*, 33(11): 1699–1713.
- Cobirka, M., Tancin, V., and Slama, P. (2020). Epidemiology and classification of mastitis. *Animals*, 10(12): 2212.
- Furgasa, W., Fayera, T., and Tsegaye, B. (2019). Isolation and identification of *Streptococcus agalactiae* and associated risk factors in bovine mastitis in and around Haramaya district, Eastern Ethiopia. *Asian J. Med. Sci. Res. and Rev.* 1(1): 13-25.
- Gitau, G. K., Bundi, R. M., Mulei, C. M., and Vanleeuwen, J. (2014). Mastitogenic bacteria isolated from dairy cows in Kenya and their antimicrobial sensitivity. *J. of the South Afri. Vet. Assoc.* 85(1): 1-8.
- Gupta, B., Gupta, V. K., Pradhan, S., Singh, R. V., & Kulesh, R. (2024). Milk hygiene, udder health and management. In *The Microbiology, Pathogenesis and Zoonosis of Milk Borne Diseases* (pp. 191-206). Academic Press.
- Lemal, P., Schroyen, M., & Gengler, N. (2025). Genetic parameters and relevance for heat stress assessment in dairy cattle of 2 udder health traits: Somatic cell score and differential somatic cell count. *J. Dairy Sci.*
- Junaidu, A. U., Salihu, M. D., Tambuwal, F. M., Magaji, A. A., and Jaafaru, S. (2011). Prevalence of mastitis in lactating cows in some selected commercial dairy farms in Sokoto metropolis. *Advances in Applied Sci. Res.* 2(2): 290–294.
- Martin, N. H., Evanowski, R. L., & Wiedmann, M. (2023). Invited review: Redefining raw milk quality—Evaluation of raw milk microbiological parameters to ensure high-quality processed dairy products. *J. Dairy Sci.* 106(3), 1502-1517.
- Monistero, V. (2022). Characterization of Staphylococci and Streptococci Isolated from Bovine Mastitis: Genotypes, Virulence Profiles and Antimicrobial Resistance Patterns of Staphylococcus aureus Strains and Streptococcus uberis Strains.
- Nikolova, M., Urumova, V., & Liuzkanov, M. (2022). Streptococcus spp. as etiological agent of subclinical and clinical mastitis of dairy cows in republic of Bulgaria. *Trakia J. Sci.*, 20(2).
- Nyakiti, A. A. (2017). *Prevalence of mastitis and antimicrobial resistance among dairy cattle in Uasin Gishu County–Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Eldoret).
- Pang, M., Sun, L., He, T., Bao, H., Zhang, L., Zhou, Y., Zhang, H., Wei, R., Liu, Y., and Wang, R. (2017). Molecular and virulence characterization of highly prevalent Streptococcus agalactiae circulated in bovine dairy herds. *Vet. Res.* 48(1): 1–12.
- Reiner, K. (2010). Catalase test protocol. *American Soc. Microbiol.* 1–6.
- Yang, Y., Liu, Y., Ding, Y., Yi, L., Ma, Z., Fan, H., and Lu, C. (2013). Molecular characterization of *Streptococcus agalactiae* isolated from bovine mastitis in Eastern China. *PLoS ONE.* 8(7): 1–8.